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IRON DEFICIENCY ANEMIA: SYMPTOMS, CAUSES AND TREATMENT

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7049781>

Annotation: Iron deficiency can cause many problems, from fatigue and hair loss to anemia. Millions of people are deficient in this micronutrient, but they may not realize it. How to identify iron deficiency anemia and what measures to take? Can it be overcome without serious treatment? How to protect yourself and your child from iron deficiency? You will learn about all this from the article.

Key words: microelement, fatigue and hair loss, iron deficiency, heart and digestion, skin and hair, stomach and intestines, heart muscle, nervous system.

70% of anemias develop due to iron deficiency. If there is a small amount of this trace element, hemoglobin molecules stop forming. As a result, the blood begins to carry very little oxygen. In other tissues, iron deficiency causes skin, hair, heart and digestive problems.

If iron deficiency is felt in the body, but anemia has not yet developed, this condition is called sideropenia or iron deficiency. Anemia often occurs in women of childbearing age, pregnant women, and adolescents aged 12-17 years. By old age, men also develop iron deficiency. Iron deficiency occurs in 60% of children born after multiple pregnancies in the first year of life.

Symptoms of iron deficiency anemia

Symptoms of sideropenia appear even before the development of anemia. Skin and hair, stomach and intestines, heart muscles, and nervous system are often affected.

Symptoms of iron deficiency are:

- dry skin;
- brittle nails;
- changes in the shape of nails, transverse lines on them;
- flowering, slow growth of hair;
- fatigue, asthenia, weakness;
- pale skin color;
- taste disturbance, desire to eat toothpaste, chalk, paint, etc.;
- awareness of strange smells;
- sores on the lips.

When hemoglobin decreases, symptoms of lack of oxygen appear - dizziness, fainting. Heart palpitations and ringing in the ears are common.

Iron deficiency anemia - tests to check

Blood tests and the following tests are performed to detect hidden or open sideropenia:

- hemoglobin;
- number of erythrocytes;
- average amount of hemoglobin in erythrocytes (MCH) and average concentration of hemoglobin in erythrocytes (MCHC);
- ferritin;
- transferrin;
- serum iron binding capacity (TIBC) and others.

In iron deficiency anemia, all parameters except TIBC decrease.

Types of iron deficiency

Iron deficiency develops gradually and occurs in several stages.

- The first stage is called "prelatent". At this stage, more iron is consumed than enters the body, but its tissue reserves are still sufficient. Prelatent iron deficiency can be corrected by dietary changes. In addition, food supplements, vitamin food can be used. Such prevention helps restore necessary micronutrient reserves and prevent the development of anemia. If the deficiency is not eliminated, the iron reserves in the tissues begin to decrease gradually. In this case, the hemoglobin level does not change, but specific symptoms may appear. In the analysis, you can find a decrease in ferritin and transferrin.

- In case of latent deficiency, it is necessary to review the diet, use special vitamin complexes. For groups at risk, such as pregnant women or children, the doctor may prescribe iron supplements at this stage.

- If the latent (hidden) deficiency is not corrected, iron deficiency anemia develops. In the case of anemia, it is necessary to take special medicines. Treatment usually continues as long as the body needs iron or until the causes of iron deficiency are eliminated.

Causes of iron deficiency

Sideropenia syndrome can develop for several reasons:

- unbalanced diet;
- stomach or intestinal diseases;
- loss of blood;
- increased need for iron.

Due to the last reason, symptoms of iron deficiency anemia occur in pregnant women and children.

The risk of iron deficiency anemia is much higher for:

- in newborns;
- in children in the period of active growth;
- in pregnant and nursing mothers;
- women of reproductive age, that is, menstruating women.

One of the main risk factors for iron deficiency anemia is pregnancy. The future mother should provide this micronutrient not only for herself, but also for her child. Before birth, about 300 mg of iron from the mother accumulates in the child's body.

Breast milk is the only source of iron for newborns. If the body of a nursing mother does not have enough iron, then the child will also have iron deficiency. Iron is involved in the formation of nerve tissue, and its deficiency greatly affects the development of the baby.

In the period of active growth, sideropenia can develop in almost 50% of children. Girls are especially prone to it during their active growth and menstruation. Due to regular blood loss during menstruation, all women are prone to sideropenia. Especially if the bleeding is long and heavy due to hormonal diseases.

Iron deficiency anemia - treatment

In the stage of latent deficiency, when hemoglobin has not yet decreased, it is enough to adjust the diet, start consuming vitamins, certain foods and vitamin supplements. The body itself enhances the absorption of iron from the intestine, and the deficiency is quickly restored.

In severe iron deficiency anemia, special medications should be taken. They allow to quickly restore the supply of iron, activate the formation of hemoglobin and erythrocytes.

Treatment of iron deficiency anemia in children

For the treatment of children, it is convenient to use drugs in the form of syrup or drops. For babies, with the help of a doctor, you can accurately calculate the dose and add drops to food. Older children can be given syrup. These types of drugs have a pleasant sweet taste and treatment usually does not cause problems.

To prevent anemia in children, you can use supplements in the form of syrup or hematogen.

When preparing doses for children, it is necessary to calculate taking into account their weight and iron content. You need 3-5 mg per kilogram of body weight per day. For a full and correct calculation, you should contact a pediatrician.

Iron deficiency is a disease that can develop secretly and does not manifest itself for a long time. In sideropenia, adequate nutrition and dietary supplements can help maintain health in adults and children. But if the symptoms of anemia appear clearly, you should not take the medicine without a doctor's advice.

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